

IMPACT OF AIRCRAFT TRAFFIC EMISSIONS ON OZONE FORMATION AT THE RIO DE JANEIRO URBAN AREA

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Abstract - Data for speciated volatile organic compounds (VOC) evaluated in Santos-Dumont Airport and Antonio Carlos Jobim International Airport in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, are reported. VOC were evaluated by gas chromatography with flame ionization detection (GC – FID) and mass spectrometry (GC – MS), following the U.S. EPA TO – 15 methodology. At Santos-Dumont Airport were quantified 1376 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ of VOCs 10 m from runway, 408 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ inside the airport building, and 116 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ outside the airport area. At the taxiway area of the International Airport a total of 190 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ of VOC were quantified. Toluene, the most abundant compound near the Santos-Dumont Airport runway, was obtained in a non-significant concentration outside the airport area. This fact suggests that this area is not noticeably impacted by air traffic. A computational model was developed using the OZIPR program and the SAPRC mechanism. Calculated ozone concentrations are higher than values for downtown area of Rio de Janeiro city. Simulated results show that, for the runway in Santos-Dumont Airport, olefins and aromatics contribute in 57% and 15%, respectively, to ozone formation, toluene being the major contributor. *Cis*-2-butene is the most reactive species regarding OH reaction.

Keywords: *aircraft emissions, volatile organic compounds, ozone, reactivity.*

Resumo - Dados da especiação de Compostos Orgânicos Voláteis (COVs) avaliados no Aeroporto Santos Dumont e Aeroporto Internacional Antônio Carlos Jobim no Rio de Janeiro, Brasil, são reportados. COVs foram avaliados por cromatografia gasosa com detecção por ionização na chama e espectrometria de massas (CG-DIC/EM), de acordo com a metodologia U.S.EPA TO-15. No Aeroporto Santos Dumont foram quantificados 1376 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ de COVs a 10 m da pista, 408 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ dentro do prédio do aeroporto e 116 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ fora da área do aeroporto. Na área de taxiamento do Aeroporto Internacional foram quantificados 190 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. Tolueno, o mais abundante composto na pista do Aeroporto Santos Dumont foi obtido em níveis insignificantes fora da área do aeroporto. Este fato sugere que esta área não é impactada relevantemente pelo tráfego aéreo. Um modelo computacional foi desenvolvido usando o modelo de trajetórias OZIPR e o mecanismo químico SAPRC. As concentrações de ozônio calculadas foram mais altas que os valores obtidos para o centro do Rio de Janeiro. Os resultados simulados mostraram que, na pista do Aeroporto Santos Dumont, as olefinas e os aromáticos contribuem em 57% e 15%, respectivamente, na formação do ozônio, sendo o tolueno o principal precursor. *Cis*-2-butenos é a espécie mais reativa com relação à reação com o radical OH.

Palavras-chave: *emissões de aeronaves, compostos orgânicos voláteis, ozônio, reatividade.*

Introduction

Environmental pollution due to emissions from aircraft is likely to increase in severity with the growth of flying. Fifteen years ago, these emissions were considered to be insignificant, but since then this point of view has been reviewed.

Since commercial aircraft spend most of their flight time in cruise mode and their emissions occur basically in the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere, research has focused mainly on the impact of their exhaust at regional and global scales. On other hand, some authors focused their attention on the air quality in the vicinity of airports.

According to data of Price and Probert (1995), amounts of emitted pollutants depend on the operation mode. Airport emissions arise from gate, taxi, take-off and landing operations. During take-off and climb-out, NO_x is the main pollutant, while during taxi / idle, CO accounts for the main emission.

In 1989, jet aircraft contributed with about 0.3% of the total hydrocarbons emitted into the ground level atmosphere, representing a relatively unimportant emission source. The typically emitted hydrocarbons are ethane, ethene, benzene and toluene (PRICE and PROBERT, 1995). Only a few studies of aircraft emissions airport operations have been published.

Underwood et al. (2001) estimated the impact of postulated airport growth scenario on the air quality in the vicinity of 23 UK regional airports for the years 2005 and 2010, focusing on the pollutants NO_2 and PM_{10} . Results for 2015 and 2030 were also reported (UNDERWOOD et al. 2001).

Popp et al. (1999) measured NO_2 / CO_2 emission ratios from in-use commercial aircraft at Heathrow Airport. Heland and Schäfer (1998) and Schäfer et al. (2000) determined CO_2 , H_2O , CO and NO exhaust mixing ratios as a function of engine power settings. Schäfer et al. (2003) determined idle emissions from in-service airplanes.

Herndon et al. (2004) simultaneously determine NO, NO_2 and CO_2 within 350 m of a taxiway and 550 m of a runway at John F. Kennedy Airport. Recently, Unal et al. (2005) quantified the impact of aircraft emissions, in regards to $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and ozone, in the Hartsfield-Jackson Atlanta International Airport, the busiest airport in the world based on passenger traffic.

To our knowledge, little work has been

published in Brazil. Simões and Schaeffer (2005) presented an inventory of CO_2 emissions by aircraft activities and a trend projection until 2023. The authors report that CO_2 emissions by the air transportation sector in Brazil increased from 5,000 Gg in 1984 to 10,000 Gg in 2002 and estimated that this value will triplicate by 2020. Several studies showed that there is a direct link between the expansion rate of the air transportation sector and the level of economic activity in Brazil (SCHAFER and VICTOR 1999; LEE et al. 2001).

Data from INFRAERO (2005) shows that about 75 million of passengers are annually transported in Brazil. Energy consumption by Brazil's air transportation sector (96.3% aviation kerosene) increased from 170 tons of oil equivalent in 1984 to 3,000 tons of oil equivalent in 2002 (MME, 2003).

Volatile organic compounds (VOC) play a major role in urban and regional atmospheric chemistry as precursors of photochemical gas phase and particulate products (FINLAYSON-PITTS and PITTS 2000). Many of them also have possible adverse health effects (SINGH et al., 1981; GROSJEAN, 1990). For this reason, were reported here data for speciated VOC in the vicinity of the two main airports in the city of Rio de Janeiro, the first work in Brazil, where VOC from aircraft emissions were identified and quantified.

Experimental Methods

The samples were collected in the two main airports of the city of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil. The Metropolitan Area of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, has a population of 11 million in an area of 6,500 km^2 .

Santos-Dumont Airport is a national airport located 1 km away from downtown ($22^\circ 54' \text{S}$, $43^\circ 10' \text{W}$, elevation 3 m). In 2004 this airport had an average of 80,000 landings and take-offs and about 5 million passengers, distributed in six air companies. The samples were collected 1.5 m above the ground in three different locations: about 10 m from runway, in the boarding area inside the building, and about 100 m away from the airport area (one sample in each local).

The International Airport of Rio de Janeiro – Antonio Carlos Jobim is located 20 km from downtown ($22^\circ 48' \text{S}$, $43^\circ 15' \text{W}$, altitude 9 m). In 2004, the airport had an average of 78,000 landings and take-offs and about 6 million passengers distributed in 17 air companies.

Three samples were collected at 1.5 m above the ground in the taxiway area. Both airports are located in a well ventilated area by the Guanabara Bay.

Samples were collected in 1.8 L stainless steel canisters. The analysis was performed by gas chromatography with flame ionization detection and mass spectrometry detection (GC-FID/MSD). The method follows U.S. EPA guidelines (U.S. EPA Compendium TO-15 Method 1999). Briefly, 100 mL aliquot of air from the canister samples were loaded on a cryo-trap ($-180\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), desorbed at $400\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and injected on a GC column where the sample is cryo-focused at $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The column was a DB-1 capillary column, $60\text{ m} \times 0.32\text{ mm} \times 1.0\text{ }\mu\text{m}$. The temperature was held at $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 min, and raised from $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $+200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at $6\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$. After leaving the capillary column, the sample was analyzed simultaneously by FID and MSD. The analyses were carried out using a Varian 3800 gas-chromatograph and a Saturn 2000 mass selective detector. The VOCs were identified by a NIST library and quantified using standard mixtures of 4 alkanes, 5 alkenes, 4 aromatics and a TO-14 standard mixture. To evaluate the results reproducibility, all samples were run by duplicate and the difference was lower than 5%. Blank runs were also performed before each sample analysis.

Results and Discussion

Results for the four sampling sites are shown in Table 1. In site 1 (10 m from runway) a total of $821\text{ }\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ of VOC were detected, which represent 60% of total compounds detected in that location ($1376\text{ }\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$). In mass units, the main compounds in order of decreasing concentrations, were toluene, benzaldehyde, isopentane, *n*-butane, *n*-pentane, 3-methyl-1-butene, 2-methyl-1-propene, 2-methylpentane, *cis*-2-butene, 1-butene and 1,1-dimethylcyclopropane which represent $1015\text{ }\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ (72% of total). Toluene accounts for 15% of total, isopentane for 14% and the two main alkanes (*n*-butane and *n*-pentane) for 17%.

In Site 2 (inside the airport building), a total of $408\text{ }\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ were detected, 54% being quantified with standard mixtures. The total level of VOC evaluated inside the building is only 30% of the value obtained near the runway. The main compounds are also different: *n*-butane, isobutane, hydroxymethylcyclopropane, acetone, propane and ethane, that accounts for 65% of

total. These results and the comparison with the main compounds found in Site 1 and in Site 3, suggest that VOC determined inside the building are probably due to anthropogenic emissions, other than aircraft and vehicles.

In Site 3, outside the airport area, a total of $116\text{ }\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ were quantified. This value is about ten times lower than the concentration obtained near the runway. In a ppbC basis the total concentration outside the airport is 464 ppbC and near the runway is 2390 ppbC, a figure five times higher. The low values obtained outside the airport may be attributed to the characteristics of that area. The area is well ventilated, near the Guanabara Bay, surrounded by a park, with low impact from vehicular emissions.

The main compounds were propane, isopentane, ethane and *n*-pentane which account for 44% of total. Propane was found to be the most abundant pollutant. A similar result was obtained in Porto Alegre, Brazil, by Grosjean et al. (1998). Propane, ethane and isopentane were also determined the most abundant non-aromatic hydrocarbons during a photochemical smog episode in Southern California (FRASER et al., 1997). In the other side, toluene, the most abundant compound near the runway, was obtained in a non-significative concentration outside the airport area. These facts suggest that the area is not noticeably impacted by air traffic.

In Site 4 (International Airport), $97\text{ }\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ of VOC were quantified. This value is 8.4 times lower than the value determined in Site 1. In mass unit, the main compounds, in order of decreasing concentrations, were ethane, *n*-butane, propane, *n*-pentane, isopentane, *n*-decane, 3-methyl-1-butene, 2-methyl-1-propene, toluene and *m*-dichlorobenzene. The sampling location, the taxiway area, is less impacted by aircraft emissions than the taxiway area in Santos-Dumont Airport.

Computational results

Computer simulations were performed using an empirical trajectory model implemented in OZIPR (GERY and CROUSE 1990) and the photochemical mechanism SAPRC (CARTER, 1990).

The details of the computational procedure were discussed in a previous paper (MARTINS et al., 2002). The model was used to construct a base case, which is a typical scenario of downtown Rio de Janeiro. It uses a combination of input data that were chosen to be

relevant and representative of Rio de Janeiro urban area. Additionally, the base case was a reference to examine the effect of aircraft emissions on the calculated ozone concentrations.

Experimental meteorological data, listed in Table 2, were collected by FEEMA (2004a) at the monitoring station located about 1 km away from Santos-Dumont Airport for August 2004. Meteorological parameters (temperature and relative humidity) are average values. Mixing heights are estimated parameters on the basis of atmosphere temperature and pressure profiles available at IAG-USP home page (2004). No experimental data are available for Rio de Janeiro. Therefore, in this work, the absolute value of CO emissions was used as adjustable parameter in order to set experimental concentrations. An error in the mixing height might be corrected by changing the emissions. The solar actinic flux was set for August 18, 2004.

The VOC/NO_x/CO emission ratios were calculated in consistence with the emission inventory for Rio de Janeiro Metropolitan Area (FEEMA 2004b) as NO_x/CO = 0.191 and VOC/CO = 0.170 (on a mass basis).

This is a crude approximation since emission ratios in the airport area are expected to be different, due to aircraft contribution to CO and NO_x emissions. The consequences of this approximation will be discussed later.

Initial concentrations of CO and NO_x were 1.01 ppm and 273.0 ppb, respectively, and were based on the experimental data obtained at the monitoring station during August, 2004. VOC initial concentration, 1.01 ppmC, and specified VOC values were obtained by Corrêa (2003) for the same location. Calculated ozone concentrations are in reasonable agreement with experimental results, with a difference less than 8.8% for the maximum value obtained at 12:00 h. A further setting was not considered necessary since this scenario was used only for comparison with the airport simulations.

VOC Composition Impact on Ozone Concentrations

In this section the contribution of the VOC mixtures determined in Sites 1 – 3 of Santos-Dumont Airport and Site 4 (International Airport) to the formation of ozone was calculated.

Ozone concentrations were re-calculated for hypothetical scenarios with conditions

identical to those of the base case, except for VOC. The total concentration of VOC, other than methane, ethanol and aldehydes, was set to 6.03 ppmC, the determined value in Site 1 of Santos-Dumont Airport. Total concentration of VOC was set identical in all simulations for a better comparison of the mixtures reactivities.

Aldehydes, ethanol and CH₄ concentrations were not determined in this work. Mean values for downtown Rio de Janeiro were used (CORRÊA, 2003). VOC compositions for each Site are presented in Table 3. Calculated ozone concentrations are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Simulated ozone concentrations for 10 m from runway in Santos-Dumont Airport (Site 1), inside the building (Site 2), outside Santos-Dumont Airport area (Site 3), in the taxiway area of the International Airport (Site 4) and downtown (Site 5).

Maximum ozone concentration calculated for Site 1 and 4 are, respectively, 77% and 34% higher than the calculated value for downtown. As will be shown, this result may be attributed to the enrichment of the mixture in alkenes and aromatics.

The concentration of secondary pollutants, mainly ozone, is related to those of precursors, VOC and NO_x, in ways that are, under many conditions, highly non-linear (FINLAYSON – PITTS and PITTS, 2000). In practice, ozone concentrations depend on VOC/NO_x ratios for this particular scenario.

In this simulation, the ratio 1.76 (in ppmC units) for the initial concentrations of VOC and NO_x, correspond to the upper region of the ozone isopleths, where ozone levels are VOC limited. Here, reducing VOC, at constant NO_x results in a reduction of ozone concentrations, while reducing NO_x, at constant VOC, actually leads to an increase in ozone levels. This value, as well as the emission ratio, was determined for downtown.

Pison and Menut (2004) found that NO_x air traffic emissions have a more important

impact than VOC emissions, particularly during the night and near the sources. VOC/NO_x emission ratios were computed for the altitude 0 – 50 m over Paris area, where one national airport and two international airports are located less than 30 km away from the downtown. Values between 0 and 1.1 (in mass units) were calculated for air traffic emissions, while values between 1.9 and 5.5 were obtained for other anthropogenic emissions. The relative contribution of aircraft emissions to the total emitted mass is +15.3% in NO_x and +2.1% in VOC. These facts led to a reduction of ozone levels through the reaction of O₃ and NO and the competition of NO₂ and VOC for the OH radical, forming HNO₃ (PISON and MENUT 2004).

For Rio de Janeiro, the emission inventory (FEEMA 2004b) used in these simulations shows a VOC/NO_x ratio of 0.89 (in mass units). This value is similar to the upper limit calculated by Pison and Menut (2004) and so a lower impact of NO_x may be expected.

Maximum values for ozone concentrations in Site 3 (outside the airport area) and in downtown were 24.6 ppb and 22.8 ppb, respectively, a difference of about 8%, which supports the conclusion that Site 3 is not impacted by airport activities.

The calculated maximum for the VOC mixture found inside the building is 70% lower than in Site 1. This fact is due to the change in VOC speciation, mainly the olefin content which decreased from 12% in Site 1 to 0.8% inside the building. As discussed in the following paragraphs, the alkenes group is the most reactive.

The influence of each group in the formation of ozone is shown in Figure 2. Ozone concentrations were re-calculated for Site 1. In each run the mixing ratio of a particular group was set equal to zero while the other fractions were not changed. For example, in run identified as “without alkanes” the fractions of the alkanes groups were set to zero, while the other fractions and the total amount of VOC were kept equal to those of Site 1 (i.e. alkanes were considered as non-reactive species in that run). The main contribution to ozone formation is from the alkenes group. Maximum calculated ozone concentration is 67% lower when this group is considered non-reactive. For aromatics, the value is 27% lower.

Figure 2 – Influence of the grouping in the ozone calculated concentrations.

Other runs were performed for each individual group, as shown in Figure 3. Again, the main contribution is from groups Olefins 1 and Olefins 2, which are responsible for the formation of 27% and 41% of ozone, respectively. Aromatics 1 group (mainly benzene and toluene) and Aromatics 2 group (mainly xylenes) contribute 15% and 9%, respectively. The contributions of alkanes, mainly group 1 and 2, are extremely low.

Since in the two airports the percentage of olefins and aromatics is higher than in downtown, ozone concentrations, in Figure 1, are also higher for both sites.

The relative reactivity of individual VOC was evaluated using reactivity scales. Different ranking scales of photochemical reactivity may be built. In a kinetic scale, the reaction with OH is evaluated by multiplying the reactive species concentration by the corresponding specific OH reaction rate coefficient. This is portrayed by the second entry in Table 4 and is an indicative of the efficiency of OH removal by the reactive species, leading to carbonyls and radicals.

Figure 3 – Percentage of contribution of each group in ozone formation for site 1 (10 m from runway in Santos-Dumont Airport).

Another approach is the MIR (Maximum Incremental Reactivity) developed by Carter (1994), Bownman and Seinfeld (1995) and Derwent and Jenkin (1991) that are shown in the last entry of Table 4 and indicate how much the compound contributes to ozone formation.

As shown in Table 4 for Santos-Dumont Airport, toluene is the most abundant compound and is also the major contributor to ozone formation. *Cis*-2-butene is the most reactive species regarding OH reaction.

Although the ranking of VOC with respect to ozone production is not identical to that from OH removal, toluene, *cis*-2-butene, 2-methyl-1-propene, 1-butene, 2-pentene, isopentane, 2-methyl-1-butene are the top-ranking compounds. Considering reaction with OH radical, benzaldehyde appears in the sixth place. In the MIR scale it appears in the last place, with a negative coefficient. This fact is due to the formation of the peroxyacetyl radical which leads to the formation of peroxybenzoyl nitrate with a rate coefficient 2.4 times higher than the coefficient for reaction with NO to form NO₂, precursor of ozone.

In any case, it is clear that the more productive species are toluene and alkenes. The species with the highest ozone productivities are not merely species that directly produce ozone themselves, but are those that increase the flow of radicals, which lead to an increase of ozone. The MIR coefficient for toluene is lower than the value for xylenes, *cis*-2-butene and 3-methyl-2-pentene. Anyway the reactivity of toluene is higher because of the high concentration of this compound in the airport area.

Conclusions

In this paper, VOC emissions by aircraft traffic in two airports of the city of Rio de Janeiro were evaluated. In Site 1 toluene was the most abundant compound (15% on a mass basis) and also the major contributor to ozone formation. Results for Site 2 show that the main compound was *n*-butane (43% of total in a mass basis) and toluene represents 3% of total. In Site 1, *n*-butane accounts for only 9% of total. These results suggest that VOC concentrations inside the building are mainly due to anthropogenic emissions, other than aircraft. In Site 3 the main compounds were propane, isopentane, ethane and *n*-pentane, characteristic of urban areas. Toluene concentration was also only 3% of total VOC mass.

Total VOC concentration in the International Airport is 7.2 times lower than the value determined in Santos-Dumont Airport.

Simulated results show that toluene and alkenes are the most important species in the production of ozone.

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Table 1 – Compounds identified in canister samples collected in Santos-Dumont Airport and International Airport, in Rio de Janeiro ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$).

Compound (using standard mixtures)	Santos-Dumont		International Airport (N=3)
	Site 1	Site 3	Site 4
Ethane	N.D	12	32
<i>n</i> -Propane	1	17	11
<i>n</i> -Butane	125	7	16
Isobutane	35	1	2
<i>n</i> -Pentane	108	10	9
Isopentane	190	12	8
<i>n</i> -Hexane	22	2	2
Propene	N.D	1	1
1-Butene	35	N.Q	1
<i>Cis</i> 2-Butene	40	N.Q	1
2-Pentene	23	N.Q	1
<i>Cis</i> 2-Hexene	5	N.Q	1
Benzene	N.D	N.Q	3
Toluene	211	3	4
Ethylbenzene	6	1	1
<i>o</i> -xylene	6	2	1
<i>p</i> -Xylene	7	1	1
<i>m</i> -Xylene	7	1	2
Total	821	70	97
(using analog compounds)			
2,2-Dimethylbutane	2	1	N.D
2,3-Dimethylbutane	N.D	1	1
3-Methylpentane	15	2	2
2-Methylpentane	42	5	2
2,4-Dimethylpentane	2	N.D	0.2

Compound (using standard mixtures)	Santos-Dumont		International Airport (N=3)
	Site 1	Site 3	Site 4
2,3-Dimethylpentane	1	0.3	N.D
Methylcyclopentane	4	2	1
1,2-Dimethylcyclopentane	20	0.3	1
Ethylcyclopropane	N.D	0.4	N.D
1,2-Dimethylcyclopropane	17	0.4	1
1,1-Dimethylcyclopropane	29	N.D	N.D
Cyclohexane	13	3	N.D
3-Methylhexane	4	1	1
1-Ethyl-2-methylcyclopropane	1	N.D	N.D
1,4-Dimethylcyclohexane	1	N.D	N.D
1-Methyl-3-ethylcyclohexane	N.D	N.D	N.D
Methylcyclohexane	N.D	1	N.D
Ethylcyclopentane	N.D	N.Q	1
3-Ethylhexane	N.D	1	N.D
2,3-Dimethylhexane	N.D	1	N.D
<i>n</i> -Heptane	N.D	1	0.1
3,6-Dimethyloctane	N.D	1	N.D
2,3-Dimethyloctane	N.D	0.2	N.D
<i>n</i> -Nonane	N.D	1	1
<i>n</i> -Decane	N.D	N.D	5
4-Methylnonane	N.D	1	N.D
4-Methyldecane	N.D	N.D	0.1
2,4,6-Trimethyloctane	1	N.D	1
3,5-Dimethylheptane	N.D	N.D	N.D
<i>n</i> -Undecane	1	N.D	N.D
<i>n</i> -Dodecane	0.4	0.4	1
<i>n</i> -Tridecane	N.D	N.Q	1
2-Methyl-1-propene	43	2	6
2-Methyl-1-butene	42	1	1
2-Methyl-2-butene	16	N.D	2
3-Methyl-1-butene	63	6	29
2,3-Dimethyl-2-butene	2	N.D	1
3-Methyl-2-pentene	N.Q	N.D	0.1
2-Methyl-2-pentene	N.Q	N.D	0.2
2,3-Dimethyl-2-pentene	4	N.D	2
2,2-Dimethyl-1-butene	1	N.D	N.D
2,3-Dimethyl-2-butene	5	N.Q	1
3-Methyl-2-pentene	5	N.Q	0.1
2-Methyl-1-pentene	3	N.Q	0.3
4-Methyl-2-pentene	2	N.D	0.2
2-Methyl-2-pentene	4	N.Q	0.2
3-Methyl-3-hexene	N.Q	N.D	0.3
1-Heptene	N.D	N.Q	1
1-Methylcyclopentene	N.D	N.Q	0.1
3-Methylcyclopentene	0.4	N.D	0.2
Cyclopentene	7	N.Q	1
2-Methylcyclopenteno	4	N.D	0.2
3,4,4-Trimethyl-2-penteno	1	N.Q	N.D
2,2,4,6,6-Pentamethyl-3-heptene	2	N.D	0.2
1-Octene	N.Q	N.D	N.Q
Cyclohexene	1	N.D	N.D
1,2,4,5-Tetramethylbenzene	N.D	N.D	2
<i>n</i> -Propylbenzene	N.D	1	1
1,3,5-Trimethylbenzene	8	3	3
<i>o</i> -Ethyltoluene	7	2	2
<i>m</i> -ethyltoluene	4	N.D	1
<i>p</i> -Ethyltoluene	6	2	1
1,2,4-Trimethylbenzene	4	1	2

Compound (using standard mixtures)	Santos-Dumont		International Airport (N=3)
	Site 1	Site 3	Site 4
1,3,4-Trimethylbenzene	N.D	2	2
<i>p</i> -Isopropyltoluene	0.2	N.D	2
Chlorobenzene	2	N.D	0.4
<i>o</i> -Dichlorobenzene	25	N.D	2
<i>m</i> -Dichlorobenzene	11	2	3
Naphtalene	N.Q	N.D	1
<i>n</i> -Butanal	1	N.Q	1
1,1,2-Trichloro-2-fluoroethane	N.D	N.D	0.1
Trimethylsilanol	N.D	N.Q	0.1
Hydroxymethylcyclopropane	N.D	N.D	0.3
1,3-Pentadiene	N.D	N.D	0.4
1,4-Hexadiene	N.D	N.D	0.2
Naphthalene	N.D	N.D	1
Benzaldehyde	128	N.D	2
Total	555	46	93

N.D – non-detected (concentration lower than $0.0001 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ detection limit)

N.Q – non-quantified (concentration lower than $0.01 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)

Table 2 – Input parameters for the simulation of the base case. Temperature and relative humidity are average experimental values for August 2004. Mixing heights are estimated values (see text for details).

Time	Relative humidity (%)	Temperature (°C)	Mixing height (m)
06:00 a.m.	77	27	425
07:00 a.m.	72	28	505
08:00 a.m.	68	29	596
09:00 a.m.	61	30	681
10:00 a.m.	57	31	837
11:00 a.m.	58	31	933
12:00 a.m.	57	32	975
01:00 p.m.	58	32	964
02:00 p.m.	60	32	906
03:00 p.m.	63	31	807
04:00 p.m.	67	30	714
05:00 p.m.	69	29	603
06:00 p.m.	70	28	495

Table 3 – Average composition of VOC mixture used for the simulation of ozone concentrations.

Compound or Group	Symbol	Reactivity k_{OH} ($\text{ppm}^{-1}\text{min}^{-1}$)	Fraction (on a ppmC basis)				
			Santos-Dumont Airport			International Airport	Downtown
			Site 1	Site 2	Site 3	Site 4	Site 5
Alkanes 1	ALK1	$k_{\text{OH}} < 5.0 \times 10^2$	0.000	0.003	0.007	0.020	0.020
Alkanes 2	ALK2	$5.0 \times 10^2 < k_{\text{OH}} < 2.5 \times 10^3$	0.001	0.006	0.016	0.018	0.021
Alkanes 3	ALK3	$2.5 \times 10^3 < k_{\text{OH}} < 5.0 \times 10^3$	0.047	0.110	0.010	0.024	0.010
Alkanes 4	ALK4	$5.0 \times 10^3 < k_{\text{OH}} < 1.0 \times 10^4$	0.107	0.048	0.054	0.036	0.047
Alkanes 5	ALK5	$k_{\text{OH}} > 1.0 \times 10^4$	0.019	0.006	0.051	0.031	0.013
Olefins 1	OLE1	$k_{\text{OH}} < 7.0 \times 10^4$	0.045	0.003	0.004	0.005	0.009
Olefins 2	OLE2	$k_{\text{OH}} > 7.0 \times 10^4$	0.079	0.005	0.004	0.023	0.005
Aromatics 1	ARO1	$k_{\text{OH}} < 2.0 \times 10^4$	0.064	0.033	0.011	0.020	0.014
Aromatics 2	ARO2	$k_{\text{OH}} > 2.0 \times 10^4$	0.013	0.016	0.084	0.072	0.022
Benzaldehyde	BALD	$k_{\text{OH}} = 1.9 \times 10^4$	0.019	0.000	0.000	0.003	0.004
Acetone	MEK	$k_{\text{OH}} < 7.0 \times 10^3$	0.000	0.005	0.000	0.000	0.001
Acetone	PROD2	$k_{\text{OH}} > 7.0 \times 10^3$	0.000	0.010	0.000	0.000	0.004

Compound or Group	Symbol	Reactivity k_{OH} (ppm ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)	Fraction (on a ppmC basis)				
			Santos-Dumont Airport			International Airport	Downtown
			Site 1	Site 2	Site 3	Site 4	Site 5
Methane	CH ₄	$k_{OH} = 9.7 \times 10$	0.592	0.721	0.685	0.675	0.795
Ethanol	ETOH	$k_{OH} = 4.9 \times 10^3$	0.006	0.007	0.019	0.019	0.007
Formaldehyde	HCHO	$k_{OH} = 1.4 \times 10^4$	0.011	0.014	0.036	0.035	0.018
Acetaldehyde	CCHO	$k_{OH} = 2.3 \times 10^4$	0.006	0.008	0.019	0.019	0.010

Site 5 – Presidente Vargas Avenue

Table 4 – Ranking, according to mass concentration, reaction rate with OH and production of ozone, of VOC collected in Site 1, 10 m from the runway in Santos-Dumont Airport, Rio de Janeiro.

Mass concentration ^a	Reaction with OH ^b	Ozone formation ^c
Toluene	<i>Cis</i> 2-Butene	Toluene
Isopentane	2-Methyl-1-butene	<i>Cis</i> 2-Butene
<i>n</i> -Butane	Toluene	2-Methyl-1-propene
<i>n</i> -Pentane	2-Methyl-1-propene	1-Butene
Benzaldehyde	1-Butene	Isopentane
3-Methyl-1-butene	Benzaldehyde	2-Methyl-1-butene
2-Methyl-1-propene	2-Pentene	2-Pentene
2-Methyl-1-butene	Isopentane	<i>n</i> -Butane
2-Methylpentane	Ciclopentene	<i>n</i> -Pentane
Isobutane	1,3,5-Trimethylbenzene	1,3,5-Trimethylbenzene
<i>Cis</i> 2-Butene	3-Methyl-2-pentene	2-Methylpentane
1-Butene	<i>n</i> -Pentane	<i>m</i> -Xylene
1,2-Dichlorobenzene	<i>n</i> -Butane	3-Methyl-2-pentene
2-Pentene	2-Methyl-2-pentene	Isobutane
<i>n</i> -Hexane	2-Methylpentane	<i>Cis</i> 2-Hexene
1,2-Dimethylcyclopropane	<i>m</i> -Xylene	<i>m</i> -Ethyltoluene
2-Methyl-2-butene	2-Methyl-1-pentene	1,3-Dimethylcyclopentane
3-Methylpentane	1,3-Dimethylcyclopentane	<i>o</i> -Xylene
1,3-Dichlorobenzene	1,2,4-Trimethylbenzene	<i>o</i> -Ethyltoluene
1,3,5-Trimethylbenzene	<i>n</i> -Hexane	<i>p</i> -Xylene
<i>p</i> -Xylene	<i>p</i> -Xylene	<i>n</i> -Hexane
<i>m</i> -Xylene	<i>m</i> -Ethyltoluene	3-Methylpentane
<i>o</i> -Xylene	<i>o</i> -Xylene	1,2,4-Trimethylbenzene

^a Units: micrograms per cubic meter.

^b Product of VOC concentration (units: ppmC) and COV-OH reaction rate constant (units: ppmC⁻¹ s⁻¹).

^c Product of VOC concentration (units: μgm⁻³) and MIR coefficient (dimensionless, gram of ozone produced per gram of VOC).